

BUCKLING ANALYSIS OF SKEW COMPOSITE LAMINATE PLATES

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SUMMARY: Up to date, while most stability studies of fiber-composite laminate plates have been focused on the rectangular plates, very little attention has been paid to the skew laminate plates. To fill the gap, this study investigates the elastic stability of skew composite laminate plates subjected to uniaxial inplane compressive forces. Based on the linearized bifurcation buckling formulation, numerical calculations of the critical buckling loads of skew composite plates are carried out by the finite element program ABAQUS. The influence of skew angles, laminate layups, plate aspect ratios, plate thicknesses, central circular cutouts, and end conditions on the buckling resistance of skew composite laminate plates are demonstrated and discussed.

KEYWORDS: buckling, skew, laminate plates, finite element

INTRODUCTION

The composite laminate plates in service are commonly subjected to compressive forces which may cause buckling. Hence, structural instability becomes a major concern in safe and reliable design of the composite plates. In the literature, most stability studies of fiber-composite laminate plates have been focused on the rectangular plates¹⁻⁵. Little attention has been paid to the skew laminate plates. It is known that the buckling resistance of rectangular composite laminate plates depends on end conditions^{2,5}, ply orientations^{2,3,5}, and geometric variables such as aspect ratios, thicknesses and cutouts^{1,2,4,5}. For skew composite plates, in addition to those factors, the plate skew angle, α (Fig. 1), should also be a key factor that influencing the buckling resistance of the plates^{6,7}.

In this investigation, buckling analysis of uniaxially compressed skew composite laminate plates are performed. The skew angle of the plates are varied among 50° to 90° . The laminate layups of these plates are $[\pm\theta]_{NS}$ ($0^\circ \leq \theta \leq 90^\circ$), $[\alpha/0]_{NS}$, $[90/0]_{NS}$ ($n = 2, 10$),

Fig. 1 Skew composite laminate plates with different edge conditions

$[90/45/0/-45]_s$ and $[90/45/0/-45]_{5s}$. The plates in analysis have different end conditions, plate aspect ratios, and may contain central circular cutouts. The critical buckling loads N_{cr} of the skew composite plates are calculated by the bifurcation buckling analysis implemented in the ABAQUS finite element program⁸. Through this study, the influence of skew angles, laminate layups, plate aspect ratios, plate thicknesses, central circular cutouts and end conditions on the buckling resistance of skew composite plates can be clearly understood.

BIFURCATION BUCKLING ANALYSIS

In the finite-element analysis, a set of nonlinear equations results in the incremental form:

$$[K_t] d\{u\} = d\{p\} \quad (1)$$

where $[K_t]$ is the tangent stiffness matrix, $d\{u\}$ the incremental nodal displacement vector and $d\{p\}$ the incremental nodal force vector. When the structural deformation is small, the nonlinear theory leads to the same critical load as the linear theory. The linearized formulation then gives rise to a tangent stiffness matrix in the following expression:

$$[K_t] = [K_L] + [K_\sigma] \quad (2)$$

where $[K_L]$ is a linear stiffness matrix and $[K_\sigma]$ a stress stiffness matrix. If a stress stiffness matrix $[K_\sigma]_{ref}$ is generated according to a reference load $\{p\}_{ref}$, for another load level $\{p\}$ with λ a scalar multiplier, we have

$$\{p\} = \lambda\{p\}_{ref}, \quad [K_\sigma] = \lambda[K_\sigma]_{ref} \quad (3)$$

When buckling occurs, the external loads do not change, i.e., $d\{p\} = 0$. Then the solution for the linearized buckling problem may be determined from the following eigenvalue equation:

$$([K_L] + \lambda_{cr}[K_\sigma]_{ref}) d\{u\} = \{0\} \quad (4)$$

where λ_{cr} is an eigenvalue and $d\{u\}$ becomes the eigenvector defining the buckling mode. The critical load $\{p\}_{cr}$ can be obtained from $\{p\}_{cr} = \lambda_{cr}\{p\}_{ref}$.

CONSTITUTIVE MATRIX FOR FIBER-COMPOSITE LAMINAE

The laminate plates are modeled by eight-node isoparametric laminate shell elements with six degrees of freedom per node. The formulation of the shell element allows transverse shear deformation⁸. For fiber-composite laminate materials, the stress-strain relations for a lamina in the material coordinates (1,2,3) at an element integration point can be written as

$$\{\sigma'\} = [Q'_1]\{\varepsilon'\}, \quad \{\tau'\} = [Q'_2]\{\gamma'\} \quad (5)$$

$$[Q'_1] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_{11}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & \frac{\nu_{12}E_{22}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_{21}E_{11}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & \frac{E_{22}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{12} \end{bmatrix}, \quad [Q'_2] = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 G_{13} & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha_2 G_{23} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where $\{\sigma'\} = \{\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \tau_{12}\}^T$, $\{\tau'\} = \{\tau_{13}, \tau_{23}\}^T$, $\{\varepsilon'\} = \{\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \gamma_{12}\}^T$, $\{\gamma'\} = \{\gamma_{13}, \gamma_{23}\}^T$. The α_1 and α_2 are shear correction factors calculated by assuming that the transverse shear energy through the thickness of laminate is equal to that of the case of unidirectional bending⁸. The constitutive equations for the lamina in the element coordinates (x,y,z) then become

$$\{\sigma\} = [Q_1]\{\varepsilon\}, \quad [Q_1] = [T_1]^T [Q'_1] [T_1] \quad (7)$$

$$\{\tau\} = [Q_2]\{\gamma\}, \quad [Q_2] = [T_2]^T [Q'_2] [T_2] \quad (8)$$

$$[T_1] = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2\theta & \sin^2\theta & \sin\theta\cos\theta \\ \sin^2\theta & \cos^2\theta & -\sin\theta\cos\theta \\ -2\sin\theta\cos\theta & 2\sin\theta\cos\theta & \cos^2\theta - \sin^2\theta \end{bmatrix}, \quad [T_2] = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\theta & \sin\theta \\ -\sin\theta & \cos\theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

where $\{\sigma\} = \{\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \tau_{xy}\}^T$, $\{\tau\} = \{\tau_{xz}, \tau_{yz}\}^T$, $\{\varepsilon\} = \{\varepsilon_x, \varepsilon_y, \gamma_{xy}\}^T$, $\{\gamma\} = \{\gamma_{xz}, \gamma_{yz}\}^T$, and fiber angle θ is measured counterclockwise from the element local x-axis to the material 1-axis. Let $\{\varepsilon_0\} = \{\varepsilon_{x0}, \varepsilon_{y0}, \gamma_{xy0}\}^T$ be the in-plane strains at the mid-surface of the laminate section, $\{\kappa\} = \{\kappa_x, \kappa_y, \kappa_{xy}\}^T$ the curvatures, and h the total thickness of the section. If there are n layers in the layup, the stress resultants, $\{N\} = \{N_x, N_y, N_{xy}\}^T$, $\{M\} = \{M_x, M_y, M_{xy}\}^T$ and $\{V\} = \{V_x, V_y\}^T$, can be defined as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \{N\} \\ \{M\} \\ \{V\} \end{Bmatrix} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \begin{Bmatrix} \{\sigma\} \\ z\{\sigma\} \\ \{\tau\} \end{Bmatrix} dz = \sum_{j=1}^n \begin{bmatrix} (z_{jt}-z_{jb})[Q_1] & \frac{1}{2}(z_{jt}^2-z_{jb}^2)[Q_1] & [0] \\ \frac{1}{2}(z_{jt}^2-z_{jb}^2)[Q_1] & \frac{1}{3}(z_{jt}^3-z_{jb}^3)[Q_1] & [0] \\ [0]^T & [0]^T & (z_{jt}-z_{jb})[Q_2] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{\varepsilon_0\} \\ \{\kappa\} \\ \{\gamma\} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

where z_{jt} and z_{jb} are the distance from the mid-surface of the section to the top and the bottom of the j -th layer. The $[0]$ is a 3 by 2 matrix with all the coefficients equal to zero. Prior to numerical analyses, the ABAQUS program has been employed to analyze the buckling of composite cylindrical panels with cutout and of isotropic skew plates. These solutions are compared with known benchmark solutions and satisfactory results are obtained⁹.

RESULTS OF THE NUMERICAL ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Laminate Rhombus Plates

In this section composite laminate rhombus plates without cutout and subjected to uniaxial compressive force N per unit length (Fig. 1) are analyzed. The length and width of the plates are $a = b = 10$ cm and the skew angle α varies among 50° and 90° . Two types of edge conditions, i.e., four edges simply supported and four edges clamped, are considered. The lamina in the plates is consisted of Graphite/Epoxy and material constitutive properties are $E_{11} = 128$ GPa, $E_{22} = 11$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = 0.25$, $G_{12} = G_{13} = 4.48$ GPa, $G_{23} = 1.53$ GPa. The thickness of each ply is 0.125 mm. Eight types of laminate layups, $[90/0]_{2S}$, $[\alpha/0]_{2S}$, $[90/45/0/-45]_S$, $[\pm\theta]_{2S}$, $[90/0]_{10S}$, $[\alpha/0]_{10S}$, $[90/45/0/-45]_{5S}$, and $[\pm\theta]_{10S}$ are studied. In the analysis, no symmetry simplifications are made and a 10×10 fine finite element mesh (100 elements) is used to model the entire rhombus plate.

Figure 2 shows critical buckling load N_{cr} versus the skew angle α for $[90/0]_{2S}$,

Fig. 2 Effect of skew angle on buckling loads of composite rhombus plates with $[90/0]_{2S}$, $[\alpha/0]_{2S}$ and $[90/45/0/-45]_S$ laminate layouts

Fig. 3 Effect of skew angle on buckling loads of composite rhombus plates with $[90/0]_{10S}$, $[\alpha/0]_{10S}$ and $[90/45/0/-45]_{5S}$ laminate layouts

Fig. 4 Effect of skew angle on buckling loads of simply supported $[\pm\theta]_{2S}$ and $[\pm\theta]_{10S}$ composite rhombus plates

Fig. 5 Effect of skew angle on buckling loads of clamped $[\pm\theta]_{2S}$ and $[\pm\theta]_{10S}$ composite rhombus plates

$[\alpha/0]_{2S}, [90/45/0/-45]_S$ composite rhombus plates. We can see that the critical buckling loads of the plates generally decrease with the increase of α angle. Under the simply supported conditions, the $[\alpha/0]_{2S}$ plates, always have the lowest buckling loads and the $[90/45/0/-45]_S$ plates usually have the highest buckling loads (except $\alpha < 60^\circ$). When the edges of plates are all clamped, the results of analyses are quite different. The $[90/0]_{2S}$ plates have the highest buckling loads and the $[90/45/0/-45]_S$ plates have the lowest buckling loads. Figure 3 shows critical buckling load N_{cr} versus the skew angle α for $[90/0]_{10S}$, $[\alpha/0]_{10S}$, $[90/45/0/-45]_{5S}$ composite rhombus plates. For plates with simply supported conditions, except the magnitude of the buckling loads, the results of analysis for these thicker plates (Fig. 3a) are very similar to those of thin plates (Fig. 2a). Comparing Fig. 3b with Fig. 2b, we can observe that the thickness does have influence on the buckling behavior of clamped rhombus plates. First, the buckling loads of the $[\alpha/0]_{10S}$ plates may increase with the skew angle α when $\alpha > 60^\circ$. Second, the buckling loads of $[90/45/0/-45]_{5S}$ plates may be greater than those of $[\alpha/0]_{10S}$ plates when $\alpha < 70^\circ$.

The last rhombus plates for analysis are the angle ply $[\pm\theta]_{2S}$ and $[\pm\theta]_{10S}$ laminate plates, in which the θ angle varies among 0° and 90° . Figure 4a shows that if the angle θ is fixed, the critical buckling loads of simply supported $[\pm\theta]_{2S}$ plates increase with the decreasing of the skew angle α . When the angle α is smaller, this increasing in buckling loads is more prominent. In addition, it seems that in spite of the skew angle α , these plates would have the highest buckling loads when the fiber angle θ is close to 45° . The only exception is the plates with α equal to 50° , where the highest buckling load may occur with θ around 60° . From Fig. 4b we can see that when the plate thickness is increased, the highest buckling loads of the simply supported $[\pm\theta]_{10S}$ plates all occur with θ around 45° .

If the edge conditions of these plates are changed to clamped edges, we can observe from Fig. 5a that the critical buckling loads of the plates still increase with the decreasing of the skew angle α . However, these plates would have the highest buckling loads when the fiber angle θ is close to 90° . The only two exceptions are the plates with α equal to 50° and 60° , where the highest buckling loads take place with θ around 45° . If the plate thickness is increased, the highest buckling loads of the clamped $[\pm\theta]_{10S}$ plates almost all take place with θ close 0° as shown in Fig. 5b. The only exception is the plates with α equal to 50° , where the highest buckling load occurs with θ around 15° .

Comparing Fig. 5 with Fig. 4, we can observe that the edge conditions have significant influence on the buckling behavior of the rhombus plates. In addition, when the plate thickness is increased, the highest buckling load of rhombus plates with angle ply laminate layup will more consistently take place at the same θ angle (say $\theta = 45^\circ$ for simply supported plates and $\theta = 0^\circ$ for clamped plates). Hence, it may be suggested to use $\theta = 45^\circ$ in the design of simply supported rhombus plates with angle ply $[\pm\theta]_{nS}$ laminate layup (n is an integer) and subjected to uniaxial compressive loading. Though, in some cases, there would have other better θ angle to achieve higher buckling resistance of plates. However, as far as the simplicity is concerned, the use of the $[\pm 45]_{nS}$ laminate layup may be a straightforward and practical choice. On the basis of the same reason, it may also be suggested to use the $[0_2]_{nS}$ laminate layup (all fibers parallel to the loading direction) in the design of clamped rhombus plates subjected to uniaxial compression.

Laminate Parallelogram Plates with Various Aspect Ratios

In this section composite laminate parallelogram plates without cutout and subjected to

uniaxial loading are analyzed (Fig. 1). The laminate layups are $[\pm\theta]_{ns}$, in which $n = 2, 10$, and θ varies among 0° and 90° . The width b of the plates is 10 cm. The length a of the plates may be either 5 cm ($a/b = 0.5$) or 40 cm ($a/b = 4$). The skew angle α of the plates still varies among 50° and 90° and two types of boundaries conditions, four edges simply supported and four edges clamped, are considered. Again, no symmetry simplifications are made in the analysis. A 10×10 finite element mesh (100 elements) is used to model the plates with $a/b = 0.5$ and a 10×20 finite element mesh (200 elements) is used to model the plates with $a/b = 4$.

Figure 6 shows critical buckling load N_{cr} versus the angle θ for $[\pm\theta]_{2S}$ and $[\pm\theta]_{10S}$ composite parallelogram plates with a/b ratio equal to 0.5 and with four simply supported edge conditions. We can see that the maximum buckling loads of the $[\pm\theta]_{2S}$ thin plates all take place when θ angle is equal to 0° (Fig. 6a). For thick plates with $[\pm\theta]_{10S}$ laminate layup (Fig. 6b), the maximum buckling loads take place at θ equal to 0° for most cases. The only exception is the plate with α equal to 0° , where the maximum buckling load may occur with θ around 30° . We can also observe that when θ is greater than 15° , the critical buckling loads generally decrease with the increase of α angle. However, when θ angle is close to 0° , this trend is totally reversed and the critical buckling loads decrease with the decreasing of α angle.

When the edge condition of the short plates is changed to clamped, we can observe from Fig. 7a that the edge conditions do not have significant influence on the trends of the buckling behavior of the $[\pm\theta]_{2S}$ thin plates (except the buckling loads are increased). For $[\pm\theta]_{10S}$ thick plates with four clamped edges (Fig. 7b), it can be seen that when θ angle is greater than 45° , the critical buckling loads increase with the decreasing of α angle. When θ angle is less than 30° , the critical buckling loads increase with the increasing of α angle. In addition, comparing Fig. 7b with Fig. 6b, we can observe that the clamped edge conditions shift the optimal fiber angle θ to values around the region 30° to 45° .

Figure 8 shows critical buckling load N_{cr} versus the angle θ for $[\pm\theta]_{2S}$ and $[\pm\theta]_{10S}$ composite parallelogram plates with a/b ratio equal to 4 and with four simply supported edge conditions. We can see that the maximum buckling loads of the $[\pm\theta]_{2S}$ and $[\pm\theta]_{10S}$ plates all take place with θ angle around 45° . For both thin and thick plates, the critical buckling loads all decrease with the increase of α angle. When the edge condition of the long plates is changed to clamped, we can observe from Fig. 9a that the edge conditions do not have significant influence on the trends of the buckling behavior of the $[\pm\theta]_{2S}$ thin plates (except the buckling loads are increased). Comparing Fig. 9b with Fig. 8b, we can observe that the clamped edge conditions shift the optimal fiber angle θ from 45° to 30° .

Finally, comparing Figs. 8 and 9 with Figs. 6 and 7, we can see that the optimal angle θ for $[\pm\theta]_{2S}$ and $[\pm\theta]_{10S}$ skew plates is influenced by the plate aspect ratio significantly. For both thin and thick plates with simply supported edges and for thin plates with clamped edges, when the plate is short, the optimal angle θ may be close to 0° . However, when the plate is long, the optimal angle θ is usually around 45° . For thick plates with clamped edges, though the optimal angle θ seems to be around 30° for both short and long plates. However, for long and thick plates (Fig. 9b), in spite of the fiber angle θ , the critical buckling loads decrease with the increase of skew angle α . For short and thick plates (Fig. 7b) the critical buckling loads may decrease with the decrease of skew angle α for some θ angle (say $\theta < 30^\circ$).

Laminate Parallelogram Plates with Various Aspect Ratios and Circular Cutouts

In these section, composite laminate parallelogram plates with central circular cutouts and subjected to uniaxial loading are analyzed (Fig. 1). The laminate layup is $[\pm\theta]_{2S}$ and θ varies

Fig. 6 Effect of skew angle on buckling loads of simply supported $[\pm\theta]_{2S}$ and $[\pm\theta]_{10S}$ composite parallelogram plates with $a/b = 0.5$

Fig. 7 Effect of skew angle on buckling loads of clamped $[\pm\theta]_{2S}$ and $[\pm\theta]_{10S}$ composite parallelogram plates with $a/b = 0.5$

Fig. 8 Effect of skew angle on buckling loads of simply supported $[\pm\theta]_{2S}$ and $[\pm\theta]_{10S}$ composite parallelogram plates with $a/b = 4$

Fig. 9 Effect of skew angle on buckling loads of clamped $[\pm\theta]_{2S}$ and $[\pm\theta]_{10S}$ composite parallelogram plates with $a/b = 4$

among 0° and 90° . The width b of the plates is 10 cm. The length a of the plates may be either 5 cm ($a/b = 0.5$) or 40 cm ($a/b = 4$). In the analysis, the diameter d of the cutout is selected to be 1 cm or 2 cm ($d/a = 0.1$ or 0.2). The skew angle α of the plates still varies among 50° and 90° and two types of boundaries conditions, four edges simply supported and four edges clamped, are considered. No symmetry simplifications are made in the analysis. Due to the presentation of cutouts, at least 500 elements are used to model the plates with $a/b = 0.5$ and at least 800 elements are used to model the plates with $a/b = 4$.

The results of analysis show that no matter of the edge conditions, N_{cr} versus θ curves for short skew plates ($a/b = 0.5$) with central holes are very similar to those of plates without holes. The only different is that the critical buckling loads of plates with holes are lower than those of plates without cutouts. Table 1 lists the reduction (in percentage) of the critical buckling loads for short skew plates with cutouts. From the table it can be seen that the plates with large hole sizes will have large reductions in the critical buckling loads. In addition, under the same fiber angle θ , the plates having small α angles usually have large reductions in the critical buckling loads. If the edge effect is considered, under the same skew angle α and fiber angle θ , the plates with simply supported edges usually (not always) have large reductions in critical buckling loads than those with clamped edges.

For long skew plates ($a/b = 4$) again N_{cr} versus θ curves are very similar to those of plates without holes. Table 2 lists the reduction of the critical buckling loads for long skew plates with cutouts. In the table, there are some negative reduction values, which means that the plates with cutouts may have higher critical buckling loads than the same plates without holes. In addition, for some skew plates (say $\alpha = 80^\circ$, $\theta = 15^\circ$, simply supported edges), the critical buckling loads may increase with the hole sizes. These phenomenon is quite different from our intuition and from the behavior of the short skew plates with central holes. However, past research did show (numerically and experimentally) that introducing a hole into an isotropic plate or a composite plate does not always reduce the buckling load and, in some instances, may increase its buckling load^{4,5,10}. This is because that the buckling load of a plate is not only influenced by cutout, but also influenced by material orthotropy, end condition, and plate geometry. From table 2 we can also find that when the fiber angles θ are less than 45° , the changes of the critical buckling loads are not significant. For same skew plates with cutouts, the change of critical buckling loads are more prominent when the fiber angles θ approach 90° . Finally, comparing Table 2 with Table 1, we can conclude that the cutout usually have more significant effect on short skew plates than on long skew plates.

CONCLUSIONS

From the buckling analyses of uniaxially compressed skew laminated plates, the following conclusions may be drawn:

1. For composite plates with same laminate layups and boundary conditions, the buckling loads increase with the decreasing of the skew angle α . When the angle α is smaller, this increasing in buckling loads is more prominent.
2. For composite rhombus plates with simply supported ends and with $[90/0]_{2ns}$, $[\alpha/0]_{2ns}$, $[90/45/0/-45]_{ns}$ laminate layups, the plates with $[90/45/0/-45]_{ns}$ layup usually have the highest buckling loads and the plates with $[\alpha/0]_{2ns}$ layup have the lowest buckling loads. When the edges of plates are all clamped, the $[90/0]_{2ns}$ plates have the highest buckling loads and the $[90/45/0/-45]_{ns}$ plates usually have the lowest buckling loads.
3. For rhombus $[\pm\theta]_{ns}$ laminate plates ($0^\circ \leq \theta \leq 90^\circ$), the highest buckling loads usually occur with θ around 45° for simply supported plates and with θ close to 0° for clamped plates. This phenomenon is more consistent when the thickness of plate is increased.
4. For skew parallelogram $[\pm\theta]_{2s}$ and $[\pm\theta]_{10s}$ laminate plates with simply supported edges, thickness has very little influence on the optimal fiber angle θ . The highest buckling loads usually occur with θ around 0° for short plates and θ around 45° for long plates. For skew parallelogram $[\pm\theta]_{2s}$ and $[\pm\theta]_{10s}$ laminate plates with clamped edges, thickness has significant influence on the optimal fiber angle θ .

5. For short skew parallelogram $[\pm\theta]_{2S}$ laminate plates with central cutouts, the plates with large hole sizes will have large reductions in the critical buckling loads. Under the same fiber angle θ and same size of cutout, the plates having small α angles usually have large reductions in the critical buckling loads. In addition, under the same skew angle α , same fiber angle θ and same cutout size, the plates with simply supported edges usually (not always) have larger reductions in critical buckling loads than those with clamped edges.
6. For long skew parallelogram $[\pm\theta]_{2S}$ laminate plates with central cutouts, the plates with cutouts may have higher critical buckling loads than the same plates without holes. In addition, for some skew plates, the critical buckling loads may increase with the increasing of the hole sizes. When the fiber angles θ are less than 45° , the changes of the critical buckling loads due to the present of cutouts are not significant. This changes in critical buckling loads are more prominent when the fiber angles θ approach 90° . In addition, the changes of critical buckling loads due to the present of cutouts for short skew plates are more significant than those for long skew plates (but not always).

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Table 1 Reduction of buckling loads for $[\pm\theta]_{2s}$ composite parallelogram plates with central circular cutouts ($a/b = 0.5$)

Simply Supported Edges										
%	$\alpha = 50^\circ$		$\alpha = 60^\circ$		$\alpha = 70^\circ$		$\alpha = 80^\circ$		$\alpha = 90^\circ$	
θ	d/b=0.1	d/b=0.2								
0°	18.04	41.20	17.85	42.52	17.75	43.50	17.73	44.16	17.67	44.33
15°	15.31	37.14	14.75	37.08	14.53	37.36	14.56	37.87	14.72	38.53
30°	15.69	37.47	13.39	33.56	12.12	31.25	11.80	30.69	12.11	31.67
45°	18.54	40.95	14.78	35.07	11.64	29.12	10.20	26.08	10.16	26.43
60°	19.63	40.95	16.04	36.55	11.79	29.36	9.279	24.20	8.397	23.14
75°	19.71	39.40	15.69	34.58	12.36	30.51	10.34	27.48	8.921	25.70
90°	22.18	41.80	16.60	34.33	13.08	30.81	12.28	31.72	11.92	33.10
Clamped Edges										
%	$\alpha = 50^\circ$		$\alpha = 60^\circ$		$\alpha = 70^\circ$		$\alpha = 80^\circ$		$\alpha = 90^\circ$	
θ	d/b=0.1	d/b=0.2								
0°	16.08	40.60	16.16	40.38	16.17	40.53	16.26	40.70	16.36	40.70
15°	13.88	35.92	13.53	34.85	13.36	34.68	13.42	35.06	13.89	35.76
30°	13.71	33.23	12.70	30.32	12.00	28.81	11.80	28.49	12.23	29.09
45°	16.19	32.62	14.91	28.63	12.83	26.47	12.11	25.46	12.34	25.61
60°	16.61	30.81	15.44	26.55	13.26	24.67	12.55	23.58	11.76	23.22
75°	15.72	29.07	13.89	24.60	12.74	22.91	11.94	22.05	11.15	21.50
90°	17.08	31.72	14.63	25.81	13.41	23.78	12.94	23.15	12.28	22.70

Table 2 Reduction of critical buckling loads for $[\pm\theta]_{2s}$ composite parallelogram plates with central circular cutouts ($a/b = 4$)

Simply Supported Edges										
%	$\alpha = 50^\circ$		$\alpha = 60^\circ$		$\alpha = 70^\circ$		$\alpha = 80^\circ$		$\alpha = 90^\circ$	
θ	d/b=0.1	d/b=0.2								
0°	1.652	3.562	1.413	3.650	-1.144	-4.041	-1.070	-4.1176	-1.032	-4.022
15°	1.082	2.191	0.880	2.207	0.470	1.898	-0.761	-1.975	-0.736	-2.777
30°	-0.262	0.800	0.795	2.365	0.754	2.364	0.769	2.398	0.802	2.450
45°	1.865	4.685	1.061	3.442	-0.188	2.401	-0.332	2.320	-0.311	2.601
60°	3.551	8.804	1.880	6.848	0.226	4.941	6.120	5.022	0.699	5.734
75°	6.869	13.82	4.109	10.85	2.796	8.948	1.821	7.275	1.773	7.201
90°	11.23	20.37	6.532	15.31	4.414	12.69	3.145	10.80	2.246	9.450
Clamped Edges										
%	$\alpha = 50^\circ$		$\alpha = 60^\circ$		$\alpha = 70^\circ$		$\alpha = 80^\circ$		$\alpha = 90^\circ$	
θ	d/b=0.1	d/b=0.2								
0°	0.090	-1.490	1.464	1.242	1.404	1.925	1.406	2.314	1.428	2.448
15°	-0.022	-0.830	0.717	0.789	1.140	1.629	1.104	1.810	1.137	1.926
30°	1.976	2.760	1.797	3.173	0.873	2.606	0.437	2.359	0.419	2.416
45°	3.386	5.296	2.775	5.387	2.161	5.119	1.998	5.072	2.058	5.180
60°	6.994	7.741	4.331	6.349	3.319	5.914	2.870	5.708	2.835	5.759